

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF FURANO COMPOUNDS.
PART XIII. 1-SUBSTITUTED DIBENZOFURANS

By J. N. CHATTERJEA

The cyclic ketone (I) has been synthesised and converted into some difficultly accessible 1-substituted dibenzofurans.

It has been shown in an earlier communication that the Kipping cyclisation may be effected at the 3-position of benzofurans yielding cyclic ketones (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 265). It is of interest to synthesise the simple ketone (I) as a source of 1-substituted dibenzofurans because as yet neither any reaction has been found which permits the direct substitution in 1-position of dibenzofuran nor any 1-monomethyl derivative has been prepared by direct ring-closure—these derivatives being usually accessible only by indirect methods (Gilman and Van Ess, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1365).

(I)

(II : R = CO.CH₂Br)

(III : R = COCH₂.CH₂.COOH)

(IV : R = CH₂.CH₂.CH₂.COOH)

(V)

2-Bromoacetyl coumarone (II) (Shriner and Anderson, *ibid.*, 1939, 61, 2705) was converted by the usual malonic ester synthesis to the keto-acid (III) and thence to the butyric acid (IV) by the Wolf-Kishner reduction. The latter, purified through the methyl ester, was cyclised in good yield to (I) by way of the acid chloride with the aid of stannic chloride. This ketone was converted into dibenzofuran by reduction with LiAlH₄ to the nicely crystalline carbinol (I : CHO in place of CO) followed by dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal or by reduction to 1:2:3:4-tetrahydrodibenzofuran and then dehydrogenation with *N*-bromosuccinimide.

Dehydrogenation of the ketone (I) with *N*-bromosuccinimide furnished the known 1-hydroxydibenzofuran (V : R = OH; Gilman and Van Ess, *loc. cit.*; Van Ess *et al.*, *Chem. Abs.*, 1938, 32, 4161). By reaction with methylmagnesium iodide in the usual way, the ketone was converted into the new 1-methyldibenzofuran* (V, R = Me) which furnished the acid (V : R = COOH; Van Ess, *Chem. Abs.*, 1938, 32, 4981; Hogg, *ibid.*, 1946, 40, 4716) by oxidation. The oxime of the ketone (I) on reduction with sodium amalgam or by LiAlH₄ (cf. Walter, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 5185) gave 1-amino-1:2:3:4-tetrahydrodibenzofuran. Preliminary experiments indicate that the compound may be dehydrogenated 1-aminodibenzofuran. A Reformatsky reaction with (I) and

*Trippett (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 419) has now prepared it in an impure state.

ethyl bromoacetate afforded the ester (VI) which, on attempted dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal, gave exclusively 1-methyldibenzofuran by decomposition (cf. Banerjee *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 408).

On general grounds, it may be expected that the tetrahydrodibenzofuran on oxidation with chromic acid would yield the ketone (VII; cf. Johnson *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1944, 66, 219). The sole product of oxidation, carried out in acetic acid, was, however, *o*-hydroxybenzylvaleric acid (VIII), previously obtained by others from hexahydrodibenzofuran by oxidation (von Braun, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 3767; Ebel, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1929, 12, 10). Attempted hydroxylation of the tetrahydro compound by selenium dioxide in acetic acid resulted only in dehydrogenation to dibenzofuran. This line of work was not pursued further when our notice was drawn to a preliminary announcement of Winternitz and Lachazette (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1955, 1393) who obtained fruitful results in this direction.†

*E X P E R I M E N T A L

β-2-Benzofuroylpropionic Acid (III).—Ethyl sodiomalonate, prepared from sodium (4.6 g.) and ethyl malonate (32.0 g.), in benzene (250 c.c.) was cooled and treated with a solution of 2-bromoacetylcoumarone (36 g.) in benzene (100 c.c.) and then refluxed for 4 hours, cooled, treated with water and washed with brine (to avoid emulsions). Benzene was removed in vacuum and the thick brown oily residue hydrolysed by refluxing with alcoholic potash (KOH 40 g., alcohol 60 c.c. and water 140 c.c.) for 1 hour. After removing alcohol by distillation, water (150 c.c.) was added to the residue, filtered from the brown sludge and acidified to provide a dirty precipitate of the malonic acid which was best purified by washing with cooled ethyl acetate-petroleum ether. This acid crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether in slender prismatic needles, m.p. 178° (decomp.), yield 18-20 g.

Decarboxylation of the acid (1.8 g.) at 180° was complete in 10 minutes; the residue was then extracted with sodium bicarbonate, clarified with charcoal and acidified to afford the propionic acid (III) (1.2 g.) which was obtained from aqueous alcohol in cream-coloured crystalline mass, m.p. 140° (yield of the pure compound, 1.0 g.). (Found: C, 65.5; H, 4.6. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.0; H, 4.6%).

γ-2-Benzofurylbutyric Acid (IV).—A mixture of the above propionic acid (10 g.), purified diethyleneglycol (62 c.c.), hydrazine hydrate (10 c.c., 85%) and KOH (9 g.) was refluxed for ½ hour; water was removed from the system by distillation and then the temperature raised to 200°-210° and maintained there for 3 hours. The mixture was

†For details see *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1956, 1817

All M. P.'s are uncorrected.

cooled, diluted with water and acidified. The *butyric acid* was obtained as a dark crystalline precipitate (8.5 g.). This was converted into the *methyl ester* by refluxing in dry methanolic solution containing 10% sulphuric acid. On distillation the ester was obtained as a homogeneous, colorless, mobile liquid, b.p. 145-48°/2.5 mm (yield, nearly quantitative). On hydrolysis with alcoholic sodium hydroxide for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the acid was obtained as snow-white crystals, crystallising from benzene-petroleum ether in colorless prisms, m.p. 82-83°. (Found: C, 70.5; H, 6.0. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.9%).

1-Keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydrodibenzofuran (I).—The foregoing acid (8.4 g.) was converted into the acid chloride by boiling with thionyl chloride (10 c.c.) for 5 minutes and then excess of thionyl chloride removed completely in vacuum. The oily acid chloride was dissolved in CS_2 (30 c.c.), cooled and treated with $SnCl_4$ (14 g.) when a crystalline complex at once separated. After 3 hours, CS_2 was decanted off, the residue decomposed with iced HCl, the whole extracted with ether and the ethereal layer washed with sodium bicarbonate. The oily residue after removal of the solvent on distillation furnished the *ketone* (I) at 160-64°/2-3 mm; yield 4.1 g. (Found: C, 77.5; H, 5.6. $C_{12}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 77.4; H, 5.4%). The viscous residue in the distilling flask on dissolving in acetone deposited crystals (ca. 2 g.), sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetic acid but soluble in chloroform and benzene. Crystallised from chloroform-acetone, this was obtained in thick plates, m.p. 216-19°. The compound was insoluble in boiling alkali and contained sulphur.

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* of the above ketone crystallised from acetic acid in long orange needles, m.p. 276° (decomp.). (Found: N, 15.5. $C_{18}H_{14}O_5N_4$ requires N, 15.3%). The *oxime* crystallised from methanol in colorless rectangular prisms, m.p. 143°. (Found: N, 7.3. $C_{12}H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 7.0%).

Dibenzofuran.—A solution of $LiAlH_4$ (50 mg.) in ether (20 c.c.) was added to a solution of the ketone (I: 0.1 g.) in ether (10 c.c.). After $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the solution was decomposed with HCl (dil.) and the ethereal layer on evaporation afforded a quantitative yield of *1-hydroxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydrodibenzofuran*, crystallising from benzene-petroleum ether in colorless fluffy needles, m.p. 109-10°. (Found: C, 76.8; H, 6.5. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 76.6; H, 6.4%).

On dehydrogenation at 300° with palladised charcoal for 2 hours, the above carbinol afforded dibenzofuran, m.p. and mixed m.p. 86°.

1-Methyldibenzofuran (V: R=Me).—A solution of the ketone (I: 0.5 g.) in ether (5 c.c.) was added to an excess of ethereal methylmagnesium iodide and refluxed for 1 hour. The product on working up in the usual manner was dried and heated in a metal bath with palladised charcoal (0.3 g.) at 280° for 2 hours and distilled in vacuum. *1-Methyldibenzofuran* was obtained as a colorless mobile liquid (0.2 g.), b.p. 125°/1.2 mm, having a characteristic odour. (Found: C, 85.3; H, 5.9. $C_{13}H_{10}O$ requires C, 85.7; H, 5.5%). The *picrate* separated from picric acid solution as orange plates, m.p. 58° (with shrinking). (Found: N, 10.6. $C_{13}H_{11}O.C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 10.3%).

Dibenzofuran-1-carboxylic acid was obtained by oxidising the material (0.1 g.) with KMnO_4 (50 c.c., 2%) for 36 hours. The acid was obtained in colorless leaflets, m.p. 232-33° (lit., m.p. 232°). (Found: C, 73.0; H, 4.0. Calc. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$: C, 73.1; H, 3.9%). The methyl ester prepared with diazomethane was obtained in prismatic needles, m.p. 63° (lit., m.p. 63°).

1-Hydroxydibenzofuran (V: R=OH).—A mixture of the ketone (I: 0.45 g.), *N*-bromosuccinimide (0.43 g.), benzoyl peroxide (ca. 1 mg.) in CCl_4 (10 c.c.) was refluxed for 6 hours. The mixture was cooled, filtered to remove succinimide, solvent removed by distillation, the residue treated with pyridine (5 c.c.) and warmed on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The mixture was acidified, extracted with ether and the ethereal solution extracted with alkali (2×10 c.c., 5%). The greenish solution on acidification gave a crystalline precipitate of the phenol (V: R=OH) (0.22 g.), which crystallised from benzene in prisms, m.p. 141° (lit., m.p. 140.5°). (Found: C, 78.5; H, 4.1. Calc. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$: C, 78.3; H, 4.4%).

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol in cream-coloured prisms, m.p. 76°. (Found: C, 73.9; H, 4.3. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 74.3; H, 4.4%).

1-Amino-1:2:3:4-tetrahydrodibenzofuran.—(i). A solution of the oxime (0.8 g.) of the ketone (I) in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) was gradually treated at 50° with sodium amalgam (total, 25 g., 2%) and the system maintained acidic by periodic addition of acetic acid. Sodium acetate separated quickly. The whole was diluted, acidified, filtered from unchanged oxime and the filtrate extracted with ether to remove the unchanged material. The acidic layer on basification afforded the amine which was isolated with ether and obtained as an oil with characteristic basic odour. This was dissolved in dry ether (15 c.c.) and dry hydrogen chloride passed into the solution. The precipitated hydrochloride crystallised from alcohol-ether in colorless needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 233-34°. (Found: Cl, 16.8. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{ON} \cdot \text{HCl}$ requires Cl, 15.9%).

(ii). An excess of LiAlH_4 (0.2 g.) was added to a solution of the oxime (0.3 g.) in ether (15 c.c.). The mixture was left overnight at the room temperature and then worked up as above to provide the amine (yield 35%). On heating with palladised charcoal, the product was found to contain some 1-aminodibenzofuran by diazo coupling test.

Condensation of Ethyl Bromoacetate with 1-Keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydrodibenzofuran.—Ethyl bromoacetate (1.5 g.) was condensed with the ketone (1.8 g.) in benzene (25 c.c.) solution in the presence of activated zinc dust. The reaction (sluggish) was initiated with a few crystals of iodine. The mixture was refluxed for 24 hours, treated with fresh zinc (1 g.) and left further for 24 hours. The yellowish mixture was decomposed with HCl , extracted with benzene, washed with dilute ammonia, dried (MgSO_4) and the solvent removed. The viscous residue (1.8 g.) was warmed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with formic acid (5 c.c., 98-100%), diluted with water, extracted with ether and the ethereal solution washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and the solvent removed completely. The thick viscous residue of (VI: 1.2 g.) was dried, mixed with palladised charcoal (0.1 g.), dehydrogenated at 240-80° for 2 hours and distilled in vacuum. The main product (1.0 g.) distilled at 130-32°/1.5 mm and identified as 1-methyl-

dibenzofuran by analysis and by direct comparison of the picrate. (Found: C, 85.6, H, 5.6. $C_{13}H_{10}O$ requires C, 85.7; H, 5.5%). The residue in the flask gave on hydrolysis a negligible quantity of an acidic material.

1:2:3:4-Tetrahydrodibenzofuran was prepared from the ketone (I) by reduction (Huang-Minlon procedure) in the usual manner. The compound was purified through the picrate (cf. Cullinane and Padfield, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1131). The compound was, however, prepared in quantity by the catalytic reduction of dibenzofuran in acetic acid in presence of Adams' catalyst (cf. Cullinane *et al.*, *loc.cit.*).

Oxidation of Tetrahydrodibenzofuran: (i) With Chromic Acid.—A solution of the compound (2.5 g.) in acetic acid (15 c. c.) was treated at 0° with a solution of chromic acid (2.5 g.) in water (2 c. c.) and the mixture left in the refrigerator for 24 hours. No ketone could be detected in that mixture. After leaving for 4 days at the room temperature, the mixture was worked up to give an acidic material (0.5 g.), crystallising from acetic acid in prismatic needles, m.p. 94°, and identified as *o*-hydroxybenzoylvaleric acid (VIII). (Found: C, 65.0; H, 6.5. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{14}O_4$: C, 64.9; H, 6.3 %).

(ii) *With Selenium Dioxide.*—A mixture of the compound (1.7 g.), acetic acid (11 c. c.), water (0.5 c. c.) and selenium dioxide (1.1 g.) was refluxed for 5 hours. Selenium separated rapidly and quantitatively. The solution was filtered and steam-distilled when some unchanged product and dibenzofuran (m.p. 86°) were obtained. The dark sticky residue proved unprofitable to work up.

(iii) *With N. B. S.*—The product of oxidation with *N*-bromosuccinimide in CCl_4 in presence of benzoyl peroxide was dibenzofuran (purified by steam-distillation) and some halogenated material.

3-Chloroacetyl coumarone was prepared with a view to synthesising β -3-benzofuroypropionic acid. Reichstein's benzofuran-3-carboxylic acid (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1937, 20, 883) was converted into the acid chloride and to the corresponding diazo-ketone (Reichstein *et al.*, *loc.cit.*). A solution of the pure diazo-ketone in ether was decomposed under cooling by ethereal HCl. The chloroketone (70% yield based on diazo-ketone) crystallised from alcohol in cream-coloured needles, m.p. 142-43°. (Found: C, 61.9; H, 3.6. $C_{10}H_7O_2Cl$ requires C, 61.7; H, 3.6 %). Preliminary experiments on condensation with malonic ester have not given encouraging results.